

(University of Choice)

**MASINDE MULIRO UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY
(MMUST)**

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING AND BUILT ENVIRONMENT

**DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMMUNICATION
ENGINEERING.**

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Attachment Report

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Place Attached: KPLC NAKURU DEPOT

**In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree course in
TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION
(ELECTRICAL & ELECTRONIC ENGINEERING)**

Industrial attachment at Kenya Power and Lighting Company.

NAKURU DEPOT

NETWORK MANAGEMENT DIVISION

OPERATION AND MAINTAINANCE DEPARTMENT.

KPLC NAKURU TOWN DEPOT.

P.O BOX 104 -20100,

NAKURU.

The industrial attachment training was designed to enable the student to apply theoretical knowledge, adopt communication skills, management and team-work, practice ethical and professional work culture and adopt Health and Safety practices in the industrial environment; in partial fulfilment of the academic requirements for various training field.

The following were expected of me at the industrial attachment:

- a) Observe all industrial safety rules and regulations.
- b) Serve the employer diligently and obey all lawful instructions set by the company policy.
- c) Not divulge any of the employer's classified information.
- d) Not absentee my self during normal working hours without the permission of the employer.
- e) Not engage in any other form of employment during working hours.
- f) Maintain the insurance cover for the period of attachment.
- g) Cooperate with fellow employees at work.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this work reflects all the activities undertaken during the industrial attachment from date...**8th May**...to ...**30th June 2023**... at **KPLC NAKURU depot, Central Rift Region**.

The report gives a record of firsthand experience in the industrial environment and it does not include any copied parts without the appropriate citation.

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I appreciate too the extended KENYA POWER AND LIGHTING COMPANY member family.

My sincere appreciation to you all...

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ABBREVIATION /DEFINITION OF TERMS.

KPLC---- Kenya Power & Lighting Company.

KYN---- Know Your Network system.

TX ----- Transformer.

HT---- High Transmission power lines (11kV &33kV).

LT---- Low Transmission (230/240 V).

LV---- Low voltage lines (240 V).

HV----High Voltage. (11Kv & 33Kv).

CT----Current Transformer

KenGen---- Kenya Electricity Generating Company

kV----Kilo Volts

kVA----Kilo-Volt-Ampere

MVA----Mega-Volt-Amperes, equal to 1000 kVA

VT----Voltage Transformer.

SCADA----Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition.

High Transmission line (HT) -refers to the 3-phase primary distribution power company

Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION.

1.1 KPLC Historical Background.

Kenya Power traces its origins to 1875 when Seyyed Barghash, the Sultan of Zanzibar, acquired a generator to light his palace which was acquired by Harrali, a Mombasa-based merchant. This led to the formation of the Mombasa Electric Power and Lighting Company whose mandate was to provide electricity. In the same year, Eng. Clement Hirtzel was requested to supply Nairobi city with electricity. This led to the formation of the Nairobi Power and Lighting Syndicate.

In 1922, the Mombasa Electric Power and Lighting Company and Nairobi Power and Lighting Syndicate merged under a new company known as East African Power and Lighting Company (EAP&L). The EAP&L expanded outside Kenya in 1932 when it acquired a controlling interest in the Tanganyika Electricity Supply Company Limited (now TANESCO) and later obtaining a generating and distribution licenses for Uganda in 1936, thereby entrenching its presence in the East African region. EAP&L exited Uganda in 1948 when the Uganda Electricity Board (UEB) was established to take over distribution of electricity in the country.

On 1 February 1954, Kenya Power Company (KPC) was formed and commissioned to construct the transmission line between Nairobi and Tororo in Uganda This was to transmit power generated at the Owen Falls Dam to Kenya. KPC was managed by EAP&L under a management contract.

EAP&L exited Tanzania in 1964 by selling its stake in TANESCO to the Government of Tanzania. Due to its presence in only Kenya, EAP&L was renamed the Kenya Power and Lighting Company Limited (KPLC) in 1983. Kenya Power Company de-merged from KPLC in 1997 and rebranded to Kenya Electricity Generating Company (KenGen) and in 2008, the electricity transmission infrastructure function was carved out of KPLC and transferred to the newly formed Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO). Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC) was re-branded Kenya Power in June 2011.

1.2 Overview of the Company's Operation.

Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC) is a company that buys electricity from generating companies then sells and distributes consumers throughout Kenya.

Electricity is purchased in bulk from the Kenya Electricity Generating Company Limited (KenGen), Independent Power Producers (IPPs) and the Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited (UETCL). Kenya Power holds and operates the national transmission and distribution grid, and is responsible for the scheduling and dispatch of electricity to more than 10,000,000 customers in Kenya.

The company also manages electric metering, licensing, billing, emergency electricity services and customer relations. The company also reinforces the existing by constructing new transmission and distribution power lines and substations in order to achieve their mission and vision.

KPLC also offers fiber optic connectivity to telecommunication companies throughout its high voltage power lines poles across the country.

Company description.

Full name: Kenya Power & Lighting Co. Ltd

Headquarters: STIMA Plaza, Parklands, P.O Box 30099,
NAIROBI.

Status: Listed in Nairobi Stock Exchange (NSE: KPLC).

Operational Status: Operational

1.2.1 Mission

- ✓ Powering people for better lives by innovatively securing business sustainability.

By striving to provide world-class products and services that delight our customers and transform lives as we ensure viability of our business

1.2.2 Vision

- ✓ Energy solutions provider of choice.

By becoming the preferred energy solution for businesses and individuals. We empower our customers to achieve more and reach their full potential.

1.2.3 Company's Core Values.

- ✓ Customer First.
- ✓ One Team.
- ✓ Passion.
- ✓ Integrity.
- ✓ Excellence.
- ✓ Accountability.

1.3 Quality policy.

KPLC is committed in providing cost effective, reliable and quality power to its customers.in the pursuit of these undertakings, suitable technologies and innovations are used to improve power network lines and consumers customer service.

The KPLC board and management and staff are committed to the effective implementation of this policies.

1.4 Safety Measures and Tools Used/ PPEs.

The most important safety measure observed is to wear the personal protective gears throughout the working process.

Before maintaining any network conductors, liveline tester is used to test if the conductor is alive or dead to avoid electrocution and possible death to persons carrying out the maintenance.

Before carrying out/working on any network, a work permit should be given by the supervisor in charge of the network.

1. Insulating Gloves
2. Helmet
3. Proper foot ware
4. Safety glasses
5. Overall gear
6. Liveline tester
7. Ring stick/hot stick.

1.5 Overview of the KPLC Nakuru Depot Departments.

1.5.1 Technical Service Department.

This department deals with the general maintenance service of power equipments in the substation. Their roles are:

1. It maintains and services the outgoing feeders.
2. Updates the softwares that enables communication to SCADA system.
3. Ensures that relays and communication protocols are working correctly to enable switching through SCADA.
4. Inspect and refill oil to the distribution transformers in the field.

1.5.2 Operation and Maintenance Department. (O&M)

This department deals with the general maintenance of transmission and distribution of network. Their roles are:

1. Inspects the power lines to mark and replace unfit circuit.
2. Replaces old weak wooden poles.
3. General maintenance of the transformers in the field e.g., replacement of charred lugs, replacement of terminal conductors on transformers.
4. General maintenance of network.

1.6 KPLC Organization Charts.

MD's & CEO's OFFICE APPROVED ORGANIZATION CHART.

Figure 1.1 MD & CEO's Office Approved Organization Structure.

KPLC ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE, SCAC APPROVED-ORGANIZATION.

Figure 1.2 KPLC Organization Structure, SCAC Approved-Organization.

1.7 Attachment Schedule and Pointers.

1. MAINTAINANCE AND BREAKDOWNS. 3 WEEKS
2. TRANSFORMER MAINTAINANCE. 3 WEEKS
3. CABLE TERMINATION. 2 WEEKS

Chapter 2. MAINTAINANCE AND BREAKDOWNS.

This section deals with the maintenance and breakdowns of utility poles which are weak, replacement of weak fallen poles, maintenance of electrical equipment such as the pole mounted distribution transformer like the replacement of transformer fuses that were blown out of due to short circuit of the conductors, maintenance of expansion fuses/cutout on HT lines, maintenance of loose conductors on utility poles, power recovery to consumers in case of a blackout or when a tree as fallen power line conductors, and also stubbing of weak utility poles and other emergence duty that may arise in the field.

2.1 Highlights of Main Activities/Work Done on Maintenance and Breakdowns.

- Replacement of damaged utility wooden poles of high transmission lines.
- Maintenance of expansion fuses/cutout on HT lines.
- Poles stubbing using pole enforcer/pole stubs.

2.1.1 Maintenance of Expansion fuses/Cutouts on High Transmission lines.

Expansion fuse is a combination of a fuse and a switch, used in primary overhead feeder lines (HT) and is

Figure 2.1 Shows the expansion fuse/cutout.

used to protect distribution transformers from current surges and overloads. An overcurrent caused by a fault in the transformer or customer circuit

or short circuit of live conductors will cause the fusing element (fuse links) in the expansion fuses to melt thus causing the switch mechanism to open, disconnecting the transformer from the line.

Figure 2.2 Shows parts of the Fuse holder; image courtesy of (Aluma-Form distribution cutout)

The fuses can also be opened manually by utility linesmen standing on the ground using a long insulating stick called a ring stick. This is usually done to isolate the part of the power system which is under maintenance, deenergize the section of HT line under maintenance for safe working environment.

Components of Expansion fuses/cutout.

1. Cutout body.
2. Fuse holder.

Figure 2.3 Shows open expansion fuses, isolating the HT feeder lines from Nakuru depot substation to Baringo line for safe working of linesmen.

3. Fusing element/fuse link.

2.1.1.1 Procedure for replacing/Installing Expansion fuses- fuse link.

When replacing the fusing element, it should be replaced with the same one of the same specifications.

For safety purposes, hand gloves are used to protect the hands from cuts. Those linesmen working on the ground should wear helmet and move away safe distance to avoid falling objects.

Figure 2.4 Shows 33kV, 40Amps fuse element/link.

- Using a ring stick, detach the cutout body from the feeder high transmission line.
- Lower the cutout to the ground and move to the suitable working area.
- Install the fuse link in fuse holder. The following procedure is used:
 - Remove the cap from the upper ferrule of the fuse holder.
 - Insert the fuse link cable end first into the top of the fuse holder and pull out at the lower end.
 - Replace the cap on the upper fuse holder ferrule and tighten with a spanner.
 - Maintain the tension of the fuse link element by tightening the fuse link clamping bolt head with wrench.
 - Cut the excess fuse link cable with a pliers.
- Install the fuse holder cutout body onto the feeder High Transmission lines using a ring stick.

Figure 2.5 Shows a linesman closing the expansion fuses using ring stick.

- Insert the ring stick hook into the fuse holder lifting ring.
- Place the fuse holder into the hinge of the cutout and remove the hook stick.
- Place the ring stick in the pull ring on the upper ferrule of the fuse holder.
- Quickly and firmly drive the fuse holder into the closed position and remove the ring stick from the pull ring carefully to avoid opening the fuse holder.

2.1.2 Pole Maintenance/ Replacement of weak utility poles.

A utility pole is a post typically made out of wood used to support overhead electrical cables, fiber optic cable for telecommuting, equipment such as transformers, and street lights. Utility pole support wires for electrical power distribution, coaxial cable for telephone communication purpose.

Utility poles that were mostly replaced were made of wood; they are prone to termite attack, and concrete. The two types of poles are used for two different types of power lines; high transmission lines, which carry higher voltages power between substations, and low voltage distribution lines, which distribute lower voltage power to customers.

Figure 2.6 Shows the fallen HT wooden pole due to termite attack.

Figure 2.7 Typical example of weak leaning pole. Effect of termite attack on poorly treated wooden utility pole.

Pole maintenance involves replacement of fallen poles and checking condition of poles in the field, pole inspection to determine their stability in supporting the overhead power line, marking the weak pole that need replacement; this should be done.

2.1.2.1 Procedure for Replacing Utility Poles/ Pole maintenance.

Most of the wooden poles that were replaced in the field were attacked by termites thus weakening the stability of the pole to support power lines.

The standard utility pole is 40ft (12M) long. When placed on the ground it is buried 6ft deep for good support. The following rule is used to determine the size of the hole to be dug.

The rule is $10\% \text{ of the pole size} + 2\text{ft} =$ is the size of the pole to be buried to ground. E.g., If the pole size is 40ft you take $10\% \text{ of } 40\text{ft} + 2\text{ft} = 6\text{ft}$. which goes to ground.

- A hole is dug 10% of pole height +2ft deep using the auger bit fitted on utility fleet hydraulic equipment.
- The new pole is fitted with the cross arm and arm braces for support.
- Transmission line conductors are detached from the old poles.
- The new pole is lifted up by the hydraulics lifting equipment from the truck/fleet and fitted into the hole.

- Soil is backfitted into the hole and tamped using the tamping bar to firmly hold the pole.
- The power transmission lines are lifted up by the hydraulic lift due to the tension of the wires from neighboring poles and mounted on top of the insulated attached to the crossarm, a binding wire is used to tighten the conductor with the insulator.

Figure 2.8 Shows KPLC hydraulic equipment operator drilling a hole using auger bit.

2.1.2.2 Procedure for Placing Pole Enforcer/Pole Stub- Pole Stubbing.

Figure 2.9 Shows stubbed weak utility pole.

- The weak pole is pulled up to a 90 degree and tighed with robes.
- A whole is dug near next to the main pole folloeing the rule of 10% of the pole + 2 fts
- The enforcer pole/pole stub is placed into the hole and soil around is tamped to firmlt holde the pole weight and its conductors.
- The pole stube and the main pole is tighed together using the the pole clamp for wooden pole.

2.2 Problems Encountered in the Field.

1. Most of the blackouts experienced by customers come as a result of the falling of weak utility wooden poles in the field that were attacked by termites and other clippers in the, this is the result of using poorly treated poles since they are cheaper to acquire.

Most of the poles in the field that were used during the last mile of electricity connectivity in Kenya are falling and are not in good condition to support power lines. This is costly in the long run as it will be expensive to maintain and replace.

2. When blackouts occur on the lower Low Voltage distribution lines, you find that a customer as to call on KLPC customer services 97771 to report the case of power failure on the customer side, sometimes customers don't call therefore remain with no power until KPLC staff notice, since the failure is not noticed at the substation level like those of high transmission that comes directly from the feeder lines

that have been fitted with sensors to notify and send signals to the control room using the SCADA system that is fitted with them at the substation.

2.2.1 Engineering Solution.

Like the HT from the feeders fitted with sensors and SCADA system to monitor the power, the low voltages from the transformers need also to have sensors and supervisory control system that can communicate to the substation team whenever the case of blackout on the customer distribution lines occurs.

The sensor design specifications as collection and transmitting of data such as voltage spikes, overcurrent, short circuits cases, that may cause power failure on LV remotely to the control team at the substation will not only reduce the recovery time of power to consumers but also monitoring the transformer working state. The sensor is to be fitted at the transformer LV network.

On the use of wooden poles verses concrete poles;

Properly treated poles should be used in cases where the concrete pole is expensive, and where power demand is low. Treated wooden poles cost between KES 10,000 to KES 12,000 for a ten-meter pole. This is far lower than KES 18,000 and KES 20,000 for a same length concrete pole.

Properly treated, wooden poles can provide an economical utility period of up to 40 years. While a concrete pole is expected to last in service for about 50 years, the difference in costs and lifespan does not make wooden poles more expensive and the benefits of using wooden poles go beyond just financial gains. In an era where every government is concerned about climate change and how to mitigate the potential impacts on the environment and human life, the sensible thing is to encourage a green economy.

Areas where wooden poles cannot withstand prevailing conditions, like in areas prone to bush fires and those that are swampy concrete should be used.

On cases where the wooden poles are to be used; soil analysis should be done to determine the effect of termite attack on pole since this will reduce the durability of the pole in the field.

Figure 2.11 Shows newly replaced elected pole

Figure 2.10 Typical example of fallen wooden pole that was placed on last mile of electricity connectivity on a soil that analysis was not done to determine the termite infestation at Mogotio in Baringo County

Chapter 3. DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMER MAINTAINANCE.

This section of the substation maintenance team basically deals with the maintenance of transformers i.e., fuse replacement, tap changer setting and replacement, visual inspection of transformers, replacement of faulty transformers, lug maintenance, replacement of blown out fuses, fuse grading for HV and LV, transformer sizing, and carrying of insulation tests e.g., megger test to check the healthiness of distribution transformers.

3.1 Highlights of Main Activities/Work Done on Transformer Maintenance.

1. HV Rod Replacement on distribution transformers.
2. Conducting insulation resistance testing using the Megger; MEGGER TEST -to determine the healthiness of transformer.
3. Replacement of charred lugs on transformer terminals- lugging process.
4. HRC fuse link transformer fuse replacement- replacing the blown-out transformer fuse due to short circuits of conductors on the LV circuit.
5. Fuse carrier replacement.
6. Replacement of lead connection conductors that were producing smoke due to overloading which generated heat that melted the conductor insulator.

Failures of Distribution Transformers.

Has been categorized into two; Major reason of failures and Minor reasons of failure.

Major Reasons.

- A. Insulation Failure.
- B. Damage to HT Coil.
- C. Damage to LT Coil.
- D. Damage to Core & Laminations.
- E. Failure to Tap Switch & Tap Arrangement.

Minor Reasons.

- a) Oil Sample not Satisfactory.
- b) Lead connections cut off.
- c) Worn-out bushing rods.
- d) Broken Bushings.
- e) Gasket Leakage.
- f) Welding Leakage.
- g) Leakage of oil through valves.
- h) Broken gauge glass.
- i) Broken vent diaphragm.
- j) Worn-out Breather.

3.2 Case Study of a Transformer Failure with Analysis.

3.2.1 Fault Details.

After a successful visual inspection of internal windings of the transformer, it was found that one phase (Blue Phase) of HV windings was severely burnt/damaged.

Figure 3.1 Shows burnt blue phase windings of the transformer.

Figure3.2 Shows faulty blue phase

3.2.2 Diagnostic Results.

Diagnostic results showed that, the failure of blue phase of HV windings was caused by overloading. The major cause of the transformer failure was due to overloading/unbalanced loading due to power theft e.g., hooking of conductors to power lines immediately before the KP&LC energy meter on the consumer unit or poor maintenance of transformer in the field. Due to this, there is overheating of the transformer oil take place and cause the release of ethylene which is the principal gas with some small amount of ethane, and methane which ultimately results to breakdown of the distribution transformer.

It was assumed that stealing of power by some of the consumers would have been done by hooking the approachable bottom most LV Blue phase conductor of the system.

This resulted into severe over loading of the transformer thus burning the windings.

3.2.3 Engineering Solution on Case Study of a Transformer Failure.

A]. Use of self-protected transformer equipped with sensors for monitoring internal condition of transformers in remote areas will help in carrying of maintenance of the transformers and possible switching of tap changer automatically to suit the load demand from consumers' side.

B]. Through deploying of Complete Self-Protection (CSP.) scheme that will enable the transformer to protect itself from overload voltages and lightening strokes.

In this scheme, transformers are equipped with primary fuses which are mounted inside the primary bushing and are in series with the primary windings to isolate the transformer in case of faults inside the transformer on

HT side and the secondary side should be fitted with circuit breakers and proper surge diverters to protect the transformer from overloads and lightening strokes on LT side.

3.3 DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMER INSPECTION AND TEST PROCEDURE.

(A) TRANSFORMER DETAILS			
New or Refurbished?	New ✓	Refurbished	Refurbishing company
Transformer make	EABLERISE	Origin	NAROK
Serial number	150604081	Date received	25/05/23
Rating	5EVA/11KV	Date tested	26/05/23
G/Number	107701	Date tested after repairs	

Figure 3.3 Shows transformer details sheet record section

Before any testing of the transformer is done, a maintenance program is set up and details of the transformer recorded in the transformer repair test sheet.

It contains the followings details;

- ✓ Name and location of the equipment.
- ✓ Dates and values of the test results.
- ✓ Voltage and serial number of the megger instrument used.
- ✓ Temperature of the apparatuses/equipment.
- ✓ Transformer Make.
- ✓ Substation number.

3.3.1 Electrical Insulation Resistant Testing – Megger Test.

Figure 3.4 Shows a megger tester.

The IR test is useful for checking if the transformer is in good condition/healthy and also to make a benchmark for future comparative tests. The technique of measuring IR by a megger-meter indicates the IR directly in megohms.

In order for the transformer to pass the test, insulation of the transformer determined should have a greater resistance than those defined by the international standards of that transformer type. If the resistance is low, it signifies that the transformer has an issue with the insulation thus require replacement/maintenance.

The following IR are recommended when testing transformer.

<u>Transformer Coil Rating Type (V)</u>	<u>Minimum DC Test Voltage</u>	<u>Minimum IR (MΩ) – Liquid-filled transformer</u>
0-600	1000	100
601-5000	2500	1000
Higher than 5000	5000	5000

The measured IR values have to be compared to factory test values if available for purposes of evaluating the results. In the absence of reliable previous test information, the following expression may be used for single-phase transformers, or single transformer winding of three-phase power transformer

$$IR = CE/\sqrt{kVA} \quad \text{where}$$

IR-- minimum 60 seconds 500 V DC IR in megohms.

C-- 30 at (C = 0.8 for tests of winding with other winding or windings earthed

E-- voltage rating of tested winding

kVA-- rated capacity of tested winding

In the case transformer under test is of the three-phase type, and all three individuals' windings are being examined as one, then:

Power Transformer Maintenance

E-- voltage rating of one of the single-phase windings (phase-to-phase for delta-connected units and phase-to-neutral for star-connected units).

kVA-- rating of the tested three phase winding.

Commonly used DC test voltages for routine maintenance are as follows:

Equipment AC Rating	DC Test Voltage
up to 100 volts	100 and 250 volts
440 to 550 volts	500 and 1,000 volts
2,400 volts	1000 to 2500 volts, or higher
4,160 volts and above	1,000 to 5,000 volts, or higher

Test voltages used for proof testing of equipment are considerably higher than those used for routine maintenance.

3.3.1.1 Procedure for Insulation Testing on Distribution Transformers.

Check the insulation resistance at the terminals with respect to ground / earth.

INSULATION TESTING ARRANGEMENT

Figure 3.5 Shows insulation testing arrangement.

- The megger test is set to inject test voltage of 1000V DC for 60 seconds. - the ohms readings are taken at 15 seconds and at 60 seconds.
- The positive terminal of the megger tester is connected to HV and negative terminal to the LV side of the transformer. The ohm measurements are recorded.
- Then the connection between HV and Earth is tested at 25sec and 60 sec. Measurements recorded.
- Finally, the connection between the LV and the Earth of the transformer, resistance measured is recorded in the table below.

3.3.1.2 Case Study of the Distribution Transformer Megger-Test Results.

BEFORE REPAIR.

INJECTED VOLTAGE.	CONNECTION	15 SEC	60 SEC
1000V DC	HV-LV	9.83 GΩ	14.76 GΩ
1000V DC	HV-EARTH	9.07 GΩ	13.40 GΩ
1000V DC	LV-EARTH	7.46 GΩ	7.43 GΩ

AFTER REPAIRS

INJECTED VOLTAGE	CONNECTION	15 SEC	60 SEC
1000V DC	HV-LV	7.94 GΩ	11.90GΩ
1000V DC	HV-EARTH	8.02 GΩ	11.50GΩ
1000V DC	LV-EARTH	8.25 GΩ	12.20GΩ

Any equipment which are superficially clean and dry that have a value less than 10,000MΩ are usually deteriorated by either the presence of moisture or carbonized parts.

3.3.2 Ratio Tests.

This is the most common transformer turns ratio test which is used to access the condition of the transformer windings and core.

It is performed as part of maintenance test to determine the problems due to poor design, assembly, handling, overloading, faulty conditions, and also poor maintenance of the transformer.

3.3.2.1 Case Study of Ratio test Results.

1. RATIO TEST											
BEFORE REPAIRS						AFTER REPAIRS					
TAP	HV VOLTS (injected V)		LV VOLTS (reflected V)			TAP	HV VOLTS (injected V)		LV VOLTS (reflected V)		
			Line Voltage	Phase Voltage					Line Voltage	Phase Voltage	
1	RY	413	ry	8.6	m	1	RY	415	ry	8.7	m
	YB		yb		yn		YB		yb		yn
	BR		br		bn		BR		br		bn
2	RY	413	ry	8.8	m	2	RY	416	ry	8.9	m
	YB		yb		yn		YB		yb		yn
	BR		br		bn		BR		br		bn
3	RY	414	ry	9.0	m	3	RY	416	ry	9.1	m
	YB		yb		yn		YB		yb		yn
	BR		br		bn		BR		br		bn
4	RY	412	ry	9.2	m	4	RY	417	ry	9.4	m
	YB		yb		yn		YB		yb		yn
	BR		br		bn		BR		br		bn
5	RY	412	ry	9.5	m	5	RY	418	ry	9.7	m
	YB		yb		yn		YB		yb		yn
	BR		br		bn		BR		br		bn

Figure 3.6 Shows Case Study of Ratio test Results transformer sheet record.

3.3.3 Visual Inspection.

Visual Inspection of the transformer is carried by vision and it entails the following;

- ✓ Inspect for physical damage and any another defects.
- ✓ Check nameplate of the transformer.

- ✓ Check all grounding cables if they are securely connected.
- ✓ Check color code for secondary wiring and size of conductor wires against specification.
- ✓ Check proper lugs that have been used in termination.
- ✓ Check VT's location physically and secondary terminal.

3.3.3.1 Case Study of Transformers Visual Inspection Checklist.

	Before Repair.	After Repair.
HV bushings	ok	ok
LV bushings	ok	ok
HV rods	ok	ok
LV rods	ok	ok
Gaskets and 'O'-rings	ok	ok
Transformer temperature gauge	n/a	n/a
Breather pressure relief	ok	ok
Oil level	Medium	High
Radiators fins	ok	ok
Paint works	Fair	Fair

3.4 Rod Replacement on Distribution Transformers.

A transformer bushing is an insulating porcelain structure that enables the passage of an energized, current carrying conductor through the grounded tank of the transformer.

Figure 3.7 Shows transformer bushing.

Bushing failure - Bushing damage can be influenced by flashover, loose connection of rod terminal and lightning strikes. The bushing rods and nuts are made of brass material 12 mm diameter for both HT and LT bushings

Figure 3.8 shows complete connected bushing, image; online

For 33 kV class bushings are used for transformers of ratings 500 kVA and above. And for transformers below 500 kVA, 33 kV class bushings, for 11 kV, class bushings are used.

Arcing horns are provided on HV bushings.

3.4.1 Procedure for Rod Bushing replacement on a Transformer.

Figure 3.9 Shows internal parts of open transformer.

- Pole mounted transformer is disconnect from the main HT power by switching off the expansion fuses using the ring stick moved to electrical plant.
- Connect the oil storage tank, oil pump and the flange with oil pipe, and fix the oil pipe with a hold hoop.
- Connect flange and drain valve at the bottom of the transformer, and open the oil drain valve of the transformer and the valve of the oil storage tank, and start the oil pump to begin draining oil from the transformer.

- The connecting flange between the transformer and the LV cabinet is removed.

- Box cover bolts are removed and collected on a bucket to avoid losing the nuts.
- Install the lifting screws on the box cover hinge and slowly lift the box cover to the height where one can operate without straining.
- Remove the soft connection copper bar attached to the transformer windings from the faulty bushing rod by untightening the nuts connecting them.
- Remove the LV bushing, and bushing fastener and check the cause of the fault for documentation purpose.
- Install the new LV bushing with a new rod.
 - Clean the position of the sealing ring of the LV bushing
 - Insert the new LV bushing into the hole.
 - Install the fixing steel plate and tighten the bolts. Tighten the bolts gradually.
- Lower the lid height of the box cover evenly to the lowest point, observe all screw holes, and see if the screw holes interfere with the sealing gasket.
- Install the box cover bolts and tighten them according to the required torque.
- Inject the oil into the transformer tank using the pump while observing the oil level at the oil gauge.
- Return the transformer to the site it was removed and restore the power supply to the transformer by closing the expansion fuses.

Proper and regular visual inspection of the transformer bushings is necessary to avoid risk of fire on the transformers.

The transformer holes should be well sealed by gaskets to avoid water entering the transformer tank when the transformer is energized to avoid explosion of transformer.

3.5 Lug Replacement – Lugging Process.

Figure 3.10 Shows Mechanical Lug. Image courtesy of online

Mechanical lug is made from high purity electrolyte copper tube, annealed and tin plated.

Lugs are required to connect conductors to the terminals of the transformers.

Poorly connected lugs get welded and tears away due to the high voltage sparks that are produced on loose parts.

For safety; the transformer is isolated from the HV HT distribution power lines and transformer

discharged before operating it to avoid possible electrocution.

3.5.1 Procedure for Replacing Old Charred Lugs on Transformers.

Figure 3.11 Shows charred lug.

- The transformer is isolated from the HV lines and discharged for safety and working condition.
- Remove the rod nuts using a spanner and cut off the old welded lug from the conductor.
- Using the hydraulic compressor equipment, insert the conductor into the new lughole and compress it hold it position.
- Tighten the lug and rod on the transformer using spanner.

- Energize the transformer by closing the expansion fuses.

The lug should be tightened firmly to avoid sparks that weld the lug tearing away.

The sparks are due to the loose connection of cables which cause leakage of current at the terminals.

Figure 3.12 Shows charred bolt and nut cut from a bushing of transformer, effect of loose lug connection to bushing.

Figure 3.13 Shows compression tool for compressing lugs to conductors.

3.6 SUBSTATION LAYOUTS AND VOLTAGE LEVELS.

The Nakuru depot substation has a total capacity of 46 MVA, which is the summation of two ground mounted transformer with a capacity rated 23 MVA each.

The substation receives 33 kVs from Soilo substation which is stepped down to 11 kVs by the transformer (TX 1) and another 33 kVs from Lanet substation is fed into the second transformer (TX 2) and stepped down to 11 kVs.

Voltage Levels.

From Soilo and Lanet substations, the Nakuru depot receives 33 kVs and transforms to 11 kVs by the power transformers.

Figure 3.14 Shows Incomer 1 feeder.

The 11 kVs are then connected into the INCOMER FEEDERS, with each transformer having its own incomer labeled as incomer 1 & incomer 2 respectively in the control room.

The two incomer feeders are then connected together through a bus-coupler feeder. Bus coupler is a device which is used to couple one bus to the other without any interruption in power supply and without creating hazardous arc.

Figure 3.15 Shows bus coupler feeder.

The outgoing feeders enables the monitoring of power, metering and switching remotely of the 11 kVs using the SCADA system.

The outgoing feeders houses the instrument transformers; voltage, and current transformers which convert the HV from 11kvs to 110V, and current to 5A for safety of energy meter use. Also housed are the trip circuit supervision relay, communication and IOT embedded systems, and tripping relays which enable the remotely switching ON and OFF of power.

Then the 11kvs from the feeders are connected to the High Transmission cables for distribution to large consumers and various distribution transformers to step down to lower voltage for home consumption.

Schematic Diagram of Substation Layout at Nakuru Depot

3.6.1 Substation Equipment and their Functions.

3.6.1.1 Lightning Arrestor.

This is a device that serves to protect the electrical equipment's from high transient voltages caused by lightning strokes and switching events in the substation. Transformer as an expensive device is being protected from such over voltages caused by lightning and also the technicians managing on such substation. Surge diverters conduct the high voltage surges on the power system to the ground.

How it works.

It protects the equipment by discharging high voltages or by bypassing surge current to the ground thus prevent flow of current to ground rather than flowing through the circuit devices as well as allowing the normal voltage continue to flow.

Lightning arrestor has two functions in a substation

- a) Limits the over voltages caused by lightning strokes.
- b) Limits the over voltages that may be caused by the switching operations.

3.6.1.2 Capacitive Voltage Transformer.

This is a type of instrument transformer which transforms 32kv voltage to 110V for metering purposes. It offers;

- a) Protection inputs to relays in a substation.
- b) Used in PLCC communications.
- c) For voltage measurement -metering purposes.

Figure 3.17 Shows VT

3.6.1.3 Isolator/Disconnecter.

Isolators have two main functions in a substation;

- a) It isolates the part of the system for maintenance activities.
- b) Re-routing the power supply e.g., from busbar 1 to busbar 2 when busbar 1 is faulty.

3.6.1.4 Current Transformer.

It converts the primary 1290Amperes to a low preferred amperes 1A or 5A for the metering.

Its offers to main functions;

- a) Protection of inputs to relays, and meters.
- b) Measurement of current.

Figure 3.18 shows a CT

Figure 3.16 surge arrester.

Figure 3.18 Isolator/Disconnecter.

3.6.1.5 Circuit Breaker.

Figure 3.19 Shows internal parts of a SF6 circuit breaker switch.

Main functions of SF6 CB are;

- a) It is used to switch on and off the power supply in a substation safely than using isolators.
- b) It offers protection from short circuit currents that may affect the power transformers.

Sulphur Hexafluoride circuit breakers are used in the substation because of its capability to open huge short circuit currents of up to 63KA without causing fire unlike isolators hence safer to operate, and also it is efficient in arc quenching because of SF6 gas used.

Figure 3.20 Nameplate of SF6 gas breaker.

3.6.1.6 Power Transformer.

Figure 3.21 Shows 23MVA ground mounted Power transformer at substation.

Two step-down oil filled ground mounted power transformers rated each at 23MVA, 33/11 KV are used in the substation and they are the most expensive equipment in a substation. They transform 33KV to 11 KV for high distribution power lines to large consumers e.g., Menengai oil refinery, spin-knit LTD, and to distribution transformers for LV distribution to low consumption

customers.

Figure 3.22 Nameplate of 23MVA power transformer 33/11KVA

3.6.2 Outgoing Feeder Maintenance.

Functions of the Feeder Panel.

1. Houses the instrument transformers current and voltage transformers.
2. Helps to measure and monitor the energy by the help of the energy meters.
3. Enable remote switching off and on of electricity.

The outgoing feeders contains some of the following devices.

Figure 3.23 Shows 11KVA outgoing feeder panels at Nakuru depot control room.

Energy Meter.

The energy meter is a measuring device that records the electric energy consumed. The meter receives 110v volts for safety purpose from the voltage transformer. The meter is calibrated to a suitable scale which enables metering

Figure 3.24 Energy meter used for metering.

Tripping relay.

Protective relays are precise measuring devices, the contacts of which should not be expected to switch large electrical loads. In some cases, the protective relay may trip a circuit breaker directly, or according to the coil rating and the number of circuits to be energized, may do so using a VAJ

Figure 3.25 Shows the tripping relay connection; internal part of the outgoing feeder.

tripping relay. The VAJ relay interfaces the protection to provide the higher contact capacity, additional contacts for tripping multiple circuit breakers, control functions, signaling and interlocking. The VAJ range comprises very reliable hinged armature relays designed to directly operate circuit breaker trip coils. Built to very high specifications, the VAJ range provides a highly flexible and reliable link between the protective relays and the circuit breakers.

Figure 3.26 Shows the trip circuit supervision relay; Type

SCADA System.

The Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), is a system that collects data, monitor and controlling system of equipment's in the industries also in the substation.

The system has a remote terminal unit that has a direct connection with meters and sensors, it also has a master terminal unit, communications system and operator workstation.

The SCADA system receives information from the high optical cable which is also offer protection to the high voltage transmission lines from lightning. The system is able to switch on and off power on sitting on the office without physical moving to the places of switching to do so.

3.7 Transformer KYN.

Before carrying out of ant maintenance on the transformer in the field the transformer details are recorded in the KYN portal system. By filling the KYN, this helps in tracking the transformer maintenance schedule for persons that are doing the maintenance and also enable to identify which make is serving the certain areas.

3.7.1 Case Study of TX Maintenance at Njoro, Mile Tatu Details.

The following are details are fed into the KYN system:

- | | | |
|------------------------------|--------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| a) Substation number – 18924 | c.) Size – 200KVA | e) Transformer Make – Mahashakti |
| b) G. No.-- 100996. | d) Serial Number—MEL/200/1490. | f) Year of Manufacture -- 2015 |

3.8 Problem Encountered in the Field.

One of the challenges that we got is that most of the transformers in the field had no properly fixed surge diverters and rod gap arrestors and those that had the rod gap arrestors were not properly installed. This posed a great danger to the transformer in the field, and thus not protected from high surge voltages.

3.8.1 Engineering Solution.

This challenge can be solved by doing regular check and maintenance to the transformer to increase their services in the field for a long duration of time without experiencing the coil burn from high voltages spike and lightening strokes. Proper inspection should be done to install the surge arrestors to avoid the coil burnt.

Those transformers in the field without the proper surge arrestors should be fixed to protect the expensive distribution transformers in the field, thus reduce the maintenance cost of repairing and rewinding of the transformer coil since copper coil is expensive to buy and import into the country.

Chapter 4. CABLE TERMINATION.

Cable termination is the connection of the conductor wire to a device such as panels, or equipment in the substations e.g., power transformer, HT cable termination, LV cable termination, current transformers, voltage transformers, and circuit breaker termination.

We have two types of cable termination methods;

1. Indoor termination.
2. Outdoor termination.

4.1 Highlights of Main Activities/Work Done on Cable termination.

1. Cable termination for three core solid dielectric (PVC/XLPE/EPR), armoured cable.
2. Cable termination maintenance of 7.2kV to 33kV.

4.2 Heat Shrinkable Termination Installation Instructions and Procedure.

Before Starting.

- ✓ Check the bill of materials and cable size construction for suitability of the kits.
- ✓ Read the manual installation instructions stepwise.

General Instruction.

- ✓ Check the cable for the presence of water or moisture. - cable containing moisture is vulnerable and can fail before its rated lifespan.
- ✓ Record the instruction resistance values before and after jointing cables.
- ✓ While directing LPG torch or kerosene blow lamp in shrink direction, keep the flame moving in a brush like motion to avoid scratching of the tubes.
- ✓ Ensure each shrinkable tube is shrunk uniformly.
- ✓ Recommended dimensional tolerances for the cable preparation is +5 mm maximum.

4.2.1 Cable Preparation Procedure.

- Peel off the cable by removing the outer sheath, the armor metal as per the following table.

Voltage Rating (KV)	L- for Indoor	L- for Outdoor	S
3.8/6.6 KV	400	600	100
6.6KV and 6.35/11KV	600	800	100
12.2/22KV	800	1000	150
19/33KV	1000	1200	200

4.2.2 Earthing Arrangement Procedure.

- a) STEP 1. Assembly of Support ring/ back up rings.
 - Spread the armor wires and insert the support ring to rest on the inner sheath and project beyond the end of the armor wire by about 5mm.
 - Fold back the amour wires to its position then bind the end of the amour wire by the binding wire.

Figure 5.1 shows back up ring.

b) STEP 2. Small braid assembly.

- Place the small tinned copper braid on the metal sheath about 100 mm above the armour cut and

Figure 4.2 Shows Tinned copper braid

- hold one end of the braid by the wrapping of roll spring twice over the copper braid (small) in the direction of the copper tape.
- Fold the copper braid back over the roll spring, wrap the rest roll spring around the braid and tighten with a twisting action.
- Extend the braid and tighten it a jubilee clamps on the armour. The process is repeated for each core.

c) STEP 3. Assembly of braid with Lug.

- Place one end of the tinned copper braid with a mechanical lug and tighten it with jubilee clamps.
- Wrap the black mastic tape/ adhesive tape over the jubilee clamps for insulation purpose.
- Pass the adhesive coated conductive breakout over the cores and pull it down in the crunch of the cable as much as possible using adequate downward force.

Figure 4.3 Shows Jubilee clamp

- Shrink the breakout into its place beginning at the center, work first towards the upper and then shrink the lower end.
- Remove the release paper and wrap stress control mastic covering 20 mm on the semi conducting screen and 10 mm over the insulation. Stretch the strip to half of its original width to achieve a fine, then edge onto the insulation.

Figure 4.4 silicon grease

- Smooth out the XLPE insulation surface for about 100 mm from the end of the semiconducting screen with the silicone grease. Place the stress control tubing over the cores and position them on the tape shield cut back and the remaining length of the tubing is parked on the XLPE insulation. Shrink down the tubing starting at the bottom working upwards. The process is repeated for the two remaining cores.
- Insert the heat shrinkable non-tracking tubing one over each core and push down to overlap the fingers of the breakout already shrunk in position. Begin

Figure 4.5 heat shrinkable non-tracking tubing

shrinking from down and proceed upwards. Shrink the tubes together up to the lower end of the stress control tube.

4.2.3 Assembly of Connector and Terminal Sleeve Procedure.

- For indoor and outdoor termination, fix the terminal mechanical lugs temporarily on the busbar.
- Align the core up to the terminating point
- Insert the terminal lug and fix it with hydraulic compression tool.
- Apply the red mastic tape over the terminal lug and over conductor.

Figure 4.6 Mechanical lug.

Figure 4.7 H. S Terminal sleeve

- Insert the lug sealing sleeve overlapping the upper end of the lug barrel.
- Shrink the tube starting from the upward towards down.

4.3 Problem Encountered in the Field.

Most of the by passing of the KPLC meters are done on meters installed on the poles. This as lead to Kenya Power getting loses in there half and end year financial statements. This is a challenge that needs a solution.

4.3.1 Engineering Solution.

This challenge can be solved through the use of smart meters like those installed on top of outgoing feeders in the substation and can be monitored from the substation team. By use of such meters in the distribution network on the consumer unit will enable the substation team to monitor the consumption of the customers voltage unit and when it is not working properly or in less consumption of the normal customer consumption. If the consumption is less the normal of the customer consumption, the substation team should be sent and check if there is a by passing or what is the problem.

Another meter should also be installed after the LV network immediately after the transformer, this meter will act as the main meter to measure and record the outgoing energy consumed by customers. This meter will act as the main summation of all the customers smart meter energy used by each customer. If the consumption on the network is higher as recorded in the main smart meter on the supply transformer than those summation of consumption from all consumers smart meters, the area connected with the supply transformer should be investigated to find out the lose of the energy which is not accounted for in the customers smart meters.

Chapter 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

5.1 Conclusion.

During the attachment period I gained the following training skills from the Kenya Power and Lighting Company- Nakuru depot. The following are the summary of activities I did during the attachment:

- a) *LV network maintenance- replacement of rotten poles, installation of stays.*
- b) *Distribution transformer maintenance – installation of expulsion fuse mounts, replacement of burnt leads, tightening loose bushings, replacement of fuse careers.*
- c) *Feeder maintenance and system reinforcement.*
- d) *Testing and commissioning of distribution transformers.*
- e) *Record keeping on the KYN transformer network.*
- f) *Safety precautions and procedures when handling LV and HV networks during maintenance.*

The industrial attachment training has enabled me to apply theoretical knowledge, adopt communication skills, management and team-work, practice ethical and professional work culture and adopt Health and Safety practices in the industrial environment; therefore, the attachment objectives have been achieved.

5.2 Recommendation.

1. The following are the recommendation on pole maintenance.

The problem of backout experience to customers can be avoided if properly and regularly maintenance of poles is done. Most of the blackout come as a result of poles falling, cutting the conductors, short-circuiting of the conductors resulting to blowing out HRC fuse link transformer fuses.

Pole visual inspection should be regularly to determine the strength of poles to support overhead power lines. Such methods that can be used to identify that weak poles are;

- ✓ The harmer test for sound.
- ✓ Drilling.
- ✓ Bore test.
- ✓ Technology such as ultrasound and x-ray to check for pole decay.

2. On Customer by Passing and Theft of Energy.

The use of smart meters that will enable remote monitoring of energy distributed from the single supply transformer network to all its connected distributed LV network. This will enable the monitoring of unaccounted energy lose that is not consumed by smart energy meters in the customer consumer unit.

The main meter is connected at the transformer LV side and other smart meters on the customer meter box.

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THE IMAGE SHOWS A 23 MVA TRANSFORMER (TX2) CONTROL AND RELAY PANEL AT NAKURU, SOILO SUBSTATION.

Internal connections of the outgoing feeders' relays and communications protocols for SCADA.

